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New Indicators for Titrimetric Determination of Fluoride by Ferric Chloride

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THIOCYANATE¹, sodium salicylate² and resacetophenone oxime³ have been investigated as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride. Many other indicators like alizarin red⁴, methyl thymol blue⁵, xylenol orange⁶, Na-rhodizonate⁷, Na-purpurin-3-sulphonate⁸ have been tried for its volumetric estimation. Even 4(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol has been studied for its titrimetric determination by various workers⁹⁻¹⁰. 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso-phenols have been prepared^{11,12} in the laboratory and used as chelating agents for bivalent metal ions. This article reports the use of these compounds as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride with acidic ferric chloride solution.

Experimental

A stock solution of 0.1M sodium fluoride was prepared by dissolving 2.1 g of NaF in 500 ml of distilled water. 0.05M ferric chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 6.7575 g of ferric chloride hexahydrate in 500 ml of 0.01M HCl, 1% solutions of the pure samples of 5-methoxy-2-nitroso phenol, 5-ethoxy-2-nitroso phenol and 5-propoxy-2-nitroso phenol were prepared by dissolving required quantity in 95% ethanol. These solutions are fairly stable and give yellow colour with fluoride ion and very low concentration is required for the titration.

An aliquot of sodium fluoride solution was taken in a 100 ml conical flask. About 2.0 g of NaCl was added to it. The contents were shaken thoroughly well and then equal volume of 95% ethanol was added to it, which was followed by the addition of

0.2 ml. (4 drops) of 1% indicator solution. It was then titrated against 0.05M acidic ferric chloride of pH 1.5 at room temperature. The end point is marked with a sharp change of yellow to red colour.

It was found that the presence of 50 times excess of Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ was tolerated in this estimation of the fluoride.

It is evident from the results that the fluoride can be determined satisfactorily by the use of 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso phenols as indicators, even when the fluoride content is very low. These compounds are found to be efficient indicators because they form less strong complexes with ferric(III) rather than iron fluoride complex.

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The Influence of Different Frequencies of Laser on the Microbial Production of Alcohol by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

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THE applications of laser to study of biological system have been reviewed by many workers¹⁻³. Both stimulating^{4,5} and inhibitory⁶⁻⁸ effects of laser on living organisms particularly on enzyme systems have been found. Combined effects of laser and some chemicals on living cells have also been explored^{9,10}. But a little or no work to study the effect of laser on the fermentations has been done as yet.

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